

The Influence of Television User Satisfaction on Youtube Media Adoption in the Cipanas Kabar Facebook Group

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ABSTRACT

TV The presence of the internet provides an additional medium for receiving various information. One of these media is Youtube. This study aims to examine the effect of television user satisfaction on the adoption of Youtube media in the Facebook group Kabar Cipanas. The method used in this research is quantitative method. The theory used in this research is the Uses and Gratifications theory by Katz, Blumer and Gurevitch and the innovation diffusion theory by Evert M. Rogers and Floyd G. Shoemaker. The data testing technique was carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics 22 (64-bit edition) 2013 software. The results of this study indicate that TV user satisfaction has a significant effect (0.006) on the adoption of Youtube Media in members of the Facebook group Kabar Cipanas

INTRODUCTION

Mass communication always involves institution and the communicator moves in complex organization. If the message is conveyed via television media, then the process is for the communicator to convey the message via audio-visual technology verbally or non-verbally and in real terms (Romli, 2016).

Each TV station can broadcast various entertainment programs, such as films, music, quizzes, talk show, news and so on. TV is a mirror of society's behavior and TV can become an addiction. TV entices us to consume more and more. TV shows how other people live and gives us ideas about how we want to live our lives. In short, TV is able to enter the recesses of our lives more than anything else (Badrudin, 2017).

Information and entertainment media today is no longer just TV. The presence of the internet provides an additional medium for receiving various information. The advancement of the primary web started when it was born World Wide Web (WWW) and the Internet Explorer within the 1990s found by Tim Berners Lee. At that point in 2004 the web created, this modern web framework was called the moment era web or Web 2.0. The moment era of the Web has capabilities user produced substance (UGC), where web clients or netizens can upload data and disseminate it all over the world.

The improvement of the utilize of web media as communication got to be progressively quick after the internet began to be open through cell phones, and after that the term smartphone (smartphone) indeed risen (smartphone). With the nearness of smartphones, there are different sorts of communication offices, beginning from SMS, MMS, chatting, email, video live, and others related to social media offices. Use smartphone which is additionally expanding over time with the highlights given by cellular producers, one illustration is that we are able observe recordings and indeed tv broadcasts fair by writing and looking for them on look motors like Google (Latifah, 2020).

The modernity of innovation has made it easier for us to get to everything that can be seen by means of the web. One thing found on the web is social media, counting YouTube. YouTube may be a video benefit supplier site streaming. This location was established in 2005 by Steve Chen, Chad Hurley and Jawed Karim (Stellarosa et al., 2018).

According to Deddy Courbuzier, after being acquired by Google at the end of 2016 for 1.65 billion US dollars or now the equivalent of more than IDR 23.3 trillion, YouTube became the best video channel compared to others, such as Vimeo and several social media such as Facebook, Instagram Twitter, Snapgram which although core the application is not a video channel but provides a video upload menu (Courbuzier, 2018). One of the reasons why YouTube is the media that people are most interested in is because it contains various types of videos ranging from entertainment, tips and tricks, to the latest news. Apart from being a media entertainment and learning, of course YouTube has the opportunity to destroy or compete with previously existing media.

Media use is almost inevitable in today's life. At home, in the office, when traveling, walking or gathering with family or friends, we always use media. If

in the past few years the internet as a communication medium had not developed, the choice of media might have been limited to conventional media such as radio, TV, newspapers, magazines and books. In contrast to the current situation, many new media have emerged, one of which is YouTube as a new media to meet information and entertainment needs.

Based on this, the formulation of the problem in this research is how much influence television user satisfaction has on the adoption of YouTube media in the Kabar Cipanas Facebook group. Therefore, it is important to carry out this research with the aim of: find out how much influence television user satisfaction has on the adoption of YouTube media in the Kabar Cipanas Facebook group.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Communication

Communication is generally defined as relationships or activities related to relationship issues or is also defined as an activity of exchanging opinions or thoughts from one person to another person or group of other people (Widjaja, 2000:13).

Uses and Gratifications Theory

In differentiate to other mass communication speculations which center on what the media does to the gathering of people, the employments and satisfactions approach centers on what the group of onlookers does to the media. The U & G hypothesis was initially created by Katz and Gurevic from "Mass Media Employments and Satisfaction Model" which he distributed for the primary time in 1974. This hypothesis risen when tv innovation created around the 1960s (Karman, 2013).

Theory uses and satisfactions alludes to how gatherings of people choose media agreeing to the requirements and wants of the gathering of people themselves. Concurring to McQuail, the concept in this hypothesis is based on the similitude of wants, needs, fulfillment and indeed the thought processes of media buyers which eventually shapes what is called an gathering of people. The similitudes that emerge from, for case, social and mental conditions emerge from the allure of the media substance itself (Nasrullah, 2019).

There are fundamental presumptions that are the center thoughts of the theory uses and satisfactions proposed by Katz, Blumer and Gurevitch. They state that there are 5 fundamental presumptions of the theory Uses and Satisfaction (Riyanto, 2017):

- 1) The gathering of people is dynamic and their media utilize is goal-oriented.
- 2) The activity in connecting require fulfillment to specific media choices rests with group of onlookers individuals.
- 3) Media competes with other sources for require fulfillment.
- 4) People have sufficient self-awareness almost their media utilize, interface and thought processes so that they can give an precise picture of that utilize to analysts.
- 5) Evaluation of the esteem of media substance can as it were be assessed by the audience.

Dissemination of Advancement Hypothesis

Advancement could be a prepare of recharging and utilizing normal assets, vitality and capital, unused courses of action of labor and the utilize of unused innovation will all lead to a production framework creating modern items (Koentjaraningrat, 2015). In the interim, advancement is an thought, hone, or protest that's seen as unused by the person or other unit that receives it. Factors and components that impact the stages of advancement dissemination incorporate: Innovation, communication channels, social frameworks and time.

METHODOLOGY

The inquire about strategy utilized in this investigate is quantitative investigate with a clear approach. Quantitative inquire about strategies are a sort of investigate whose details are orderly, arranged and clearly organized from the begin until the creation of the investigate plan. Researchers who are oriented towards quantitative research emphasize how important the hypothesis or research question is in a study, because it will determine the sample, choose the type/type of instrument and analysis techniques used (Yusuf, 2014). In quantitative research, it is necessary to use theory to explain the variables used, or in other words, every variable used must have a theory. Variables that have no theory must be abandoned until the theory is found or replace variables that are in accordance with the theory (Bungin, 2017).

Population and Sample

Populace is all objects and investigate comprising of people, objects, creatures, plants, side effects, values, writings, or occasions as information sources that have certain characteristics in a consider (Zulfah, 2018). The populace in this ponder were gather members Facebook Cipanas news come to 66,987 individuals. In carrying out the testing method, analysts utilized the likelihood testing strategy. This strategy could be a testing procedure that gives break even with opportunity for each component (part) of the populace to be chosen as a part of the test (Fitria & Ariva, 2018). Based on the number of populations taken, to decide the test agent employing a inspecting method based on the Slovin Equation (Imran, 2017). So the test from this think about is $n = 66,987 / (1 + 66,987 (0.1)^2) = 100$. So, the number of tests considered was 100 respondents.

Analysis Process

A few stages carried out in this inquire about are
Information Collection Strategies

The primary information collection is library investigate (library research). Library inquire about could be a information collection strategy carried out by analysts by looking at hypotheses, suppositions and fundamental thoughts contained in print media, especially books that bolster and are pertinent to issues examined within the investigate (Sari & Asmendri, 2020).

The moment information collection is field investigate (field inquire about). This field investigate was gotten by going directly into the field on the chosen objects, specifically by disseminating surveys. A survey may be a list that contains a arrangement of articulations almost a matter or a field. This survey is

expecting as a list of questions to get answers from respondents (Rahmawati et al., 2020).

Data Analysis

Information investigation is an action after information from all respondents has been collected. Exercises in information investigation are gathering information based on factors and sort of respondent, organizing information based on factors from all respondents, displaying information from each variable considered, carrying out calculations to reply the issue definition and carrying out calculations to test theories that have been submitted (Mustafa, Gusdiyanto, & Victoria, 2020).

In the interim, the information investigation carried out in this investigate is as takes after:

- 1) Validity & Unwavering quality Test
- 2) Normality test
- 3) Multicollinearity Test
- 4) Heteroscedasticity Test
- 5) Autocorrelation Test
- 6) Different Direct Relapse Test

Information is prepared factually for the purposes of investigation and theory testing utilizing program tools IBM SPSS Insights 22 (64-bit version) 2013.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Description of Research Location

The inquire about area is in Cipanas Locale, Cianjur Rule. The inquire about area is between 106°57'30" East Longitude to 107°04'00" East Longitude and 06°39'00" South Scope up to 06°47'30" South scope. Based on information from the Central Measurements Organization Cianjur Rule In 2017, the range of Cipanas Area was 67.2 km² with a populace in 2017 of 108,115 individuals. Cipanas Locale has seven towns, specifically Batulawang Town, Ciloto Town, Cimacan Town, Cipanas Town, Palasari Town, Sindangjaya Town, and Sindanglaya Town (Panji, 2017).

This research in Cipanas District was carried out through the Kabar Cipanas Facebook group. The Cipanas news Facebook group has 66,646 members. Facebook is a social media site that was launched in 2004. Since this site became accessible in Indonesia, many people have used it, so they are no longer unfamiliar with the term Facebook. Facebook is a social networking site on the internet that allows users to interact and share data with other users. Currently Facebook is the largest social media in terms of global reach and number of active users. Data from Pew Research Center shows that while the adoption of other social media is starting to reach a critical point in terms of its use, Facebook remains far ahead of other social media and continues to increase in use in the world (Yasya et al., 2019).

One of the social facilities of the Facebook social networking site is groups. Facebook groups are one of the services provided by the social networking site Facebook which can be used to share videos, links, comments and photos which can be commented on by other group members. The purpose of forming a Facebook group is as a community forum for exchanging information, discussing

with members who are interested in the topic of the group. Therefore, research conducted in the Kabar Cipanas Facebook Group will be effective in reaching a wider range of respondents.

Description of Respondent Characteristics Data

The characteristics of respondents in this study include group members Facebook Cipanas News. Totaling 66,646 people, with a sample of 100 people. The questionnaire was distributed using an application from Google Form, until the specified time limit there were 102 respondents who filled out the questionnaire and it could be used. Respondent characteristics consist of gender, age, active TV user or not, active YouTube user or not, duration of watching TV in a day and duration of watching YouTube in a day with the following data.

Figure 1. Gender

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

The picture shows that the majority of respondents' gender is female with a percentage of 64.4%, while the remainder are male, amounting to 35.6%. Based on this data, group members Facebook Cipanas News who filled out the questionnaire were dominated by women.

Figure 2. Age

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

From the picture above we can see that the questionnaire fillers consisted of 84.2% aged 5-25 years, 10.9% 26-40 years old, 3.9% aged 41-55 years old and 1% aged 24-50 years.

Figure 3. Active TV Users the Image Above Shows

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

That the majority of respondents were active TV users with 78.2%, while 21.8% were not active TV users. Based on this data, group members Facebook Cipanas News who filled out the questionnaire were dominated by active TV users.

Figure 4. Active Youtube Users the Image Above Shows
 (Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

That the majority of respondents are active YouTube users with 95%, while the rest are not active YouTube users. Based on this data, group members Facebook Cipanas News who filled out the questionnaire were dominated by active YouTube users.

Figure 5. TV Watching Duration the Picture Above Shows
 (Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

That the majority of respondents are TV viewers in the light category, namely 0-4 hours a day with a percentage of 78.2%, while 13.9% are not is a heavy audience category, namely more than 4 hours a day.

Figure 6. Youtube Watching Duration the Image
 (Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

Youtube Watching Duration The image above shows that the majority of respondents are moderate YouTube viewers, namely 20-80 minutes a day, with a percentage of 49.5%, while 25.7% are heavy viewers, namely more than 80 minutes a day. Apart from that, 24.8% fall into the light category with a viewing duration of 0-<20 minutes a day.

Validity & Reliability Test

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. This validity test uses a testing technique that is often used by researchers to test validity, namely using correlation Bivariate Pearson (Moment Products Pearson). According to Ghozali, a question is said to be valid if the

significance level is below 0.05 (Ratu et al., 2020). If $r_{count} \geq r_{table}$ (2-sided test with sig. 0.05) then the instrument or question items are declared valid.

Meanwhile, reliability testing is actually a tool for measuring a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable or construct. A questionnaire is said to be reliable or reliable if a person's answers to questions are consistent or stable over time. According to Ghozali, questionnaire items are said to be reliable (feasible) if $\alpha > 0.06$ and is said to be unreliable if $\alpha < 0.06$ (Zahra & Rina, 2018).

The validity test results show that all question items ($r_{count} > 0.1966$ (r_{table})), so the question items are declared valid. Likewise, the reliability test shows that the variable X questionnaire is declared reliable $\alpha = 0.882 > 0.06$ and the variable Y questionnaire is declared reliable with $\alpha = 0.849 > 0.06$.

Normality Test

Table 1. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	731.514.474
	Absolute	.118
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.118
	Negative	-.057
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.178
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.125

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

The normality test aims to find out whether the residual values are normally distributed or not. A good regression model has residual values that are normally distributed. Normally distributed data will reduce the possibility of bias (Apriyono & Taman, 2013).

Basis for decision making:

- If the significance value is > 0.05 , then the residual value is normally distributed.
- If the significance value is < 0.05 , then the residual value is not normally distributed.

Based on the normality test results, it is known that the significance value is $0.125 > 0.05$, then it can be concluded that the residual values are normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	58,844	4,689		12,548	,000		
	Keinginan	-,857	,675	-,173	-1,269	,207	,488	2,048
	Kebutuhan	-,546	,450	-,177	-1,214	,228	,426	2,345
	Motif	,224	,528	,059	,424	,673	,474	2,108
	Kepuasan	2,014	,620	,525	3,250	,002	,347	2,880

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

Test Multicollinearity is a situation where there is a perfect or near perfect linear relationship between the independent variables in the regression model. The purpose of the multicollinearity test is to test whether the regression model finds a correlation between the independent variables. A good regression model should be free from correlation between independent variables (Denziana et al., 2014).

Basis for decision making:

- If the VIF is below or < 10 and Tolerance value above > 0.1 then multicollinearity does not occur.
- If the VIF is above or > 10 and Tolerance value below < 0.1 then multicollinearity occurs.

Based on table 4.6, it is known that the VIF value of the desire variable (X1) is $2.048 < 10$, the variable needs (X2) is $2.345 < 10$, Motive variable (X3) is $2.108 < 10$, satisfaction variable (X3) is $2.880 < 10$ and the tolerance value of the desire variable (X1) $0.488 > 0.1$, the needs variable (X2) $0.426 > 0.1$, the motive variable (X3) $474 > 0.1$, the satisfaction variable (X4) $347 > 0.1$ then the data multicollinearity does not occur.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 7. Heteroscedasticity Test
 (Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

Test Heteroscedasticity aims to test whether inequality occurs in the regression model variance from the residual of one observation to another observation. To detect there whether there is heteroscedasticity by looking at the pattern of dots on the regression plots. If the points spread in an unclear pattern above and below the number 0 on the Y axis then there is no heteroscedasticity problem (Supriyadi et al., 2017).

From the picture above, we can draw the conclusion from the heteroscedasticity test that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity because the data points are spread above and below or around the number 0, the points do not gather only at the top or bottom, the distribution of the data points is not may form a wavy pattern that widens then narrows and widens again, and the distribution of data points has no pattern.

Autocorrelation Test

Table 3. Autocorrelation Test Results

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.372 ^a	.139	.102	7.109	1.793

a. Predictors: (Constant), Kepuasan, Motif, Keinginan, Kebutuhan

b. Dependent Variable: Pengadopsian Youtube

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

Autocorrelation test to determine whether a regression model has a correlation between confounding errors in period t and confounding errors in period t-1 (the previous period). The test used is the Durbin – Watson Test (DW Test) (Sabrudin & Suhendra, 2019).

Basis for decision making:

- If $d < dL$ or $d > 4-dL$, then the null hypothesis is rejected, meaning there is autocorrelation.
- If $dU < d < 4-dU$, then the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning there is no autocorrelation.
- If $dL < d < dU$ or $4-dU < d < 4-dL$, then it means there is no conclusion.

Durbin Watson Autocorrelation Test Results: Result = $dU < d < 4-dU = 1,758 < 1,793 < 2,242$

Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis is a form of linear regression analysis where there is more than one independent variable. This multiple regression analysis was carried out on the dimensions included in the construct of TV user satisfaction (as an independent variable) to obtain a variant of the YouTube media adoption variable (as a dependent variable). The equation for multiple regression is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_nX_n$$

Information

b_1, b_2, b_n = estimated regression coefficient

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results F Test
 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	772.759	4	193.190	3.822	.006 ^b
1 Residual	4.801.351	95	50.541		
Total	5.574.110	99			

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

Basis for Decision Making:

- If the significance value is < 0.05 , or $F \text{ count} > F \text{ table}$ then there is a simultaneous influence of variable X on variable Y.

- If the significance value is > 0.05 , or $F \text{ count} < F \text{ table}$ then there is no simultaneous influence of variable X on variable Y.

Judging from the table, the F-test shows that the F value is 3.822 with a significance of 0.006 ($0.006 < 0.05$), H_0 is rejected). So, this can be interpreted simultaneously as a significant influence of TV User Satisfaction on YouTube Media Adoption.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results T Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	58.844	4.689		12.548	.000
Keinginan (X1)	-.857	.675	-.173	-1.269	.207
1 Kebutuhan X2	-.546	.450	-.177	-1.214	.228
Motif (X3)	.224	.528	.059	.424	.673
Kepuasan (X4)	2.014	.620	.525	3.250	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Penerimaan Youtube

(Source: Researcher's Process, 2021)

Basis for decision making:

• If the significance value is < 0.05 , or $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ then there is an influence of variable X on variable Y.

• If the significance value is > 0.05 , or $t \text{ count} < t \text{ table}$ then there is no influence of variable X on variable Y.

Judging from the table, the t-test shows that:

• Desire has a significance value of 0.207 ($0.207 > 0.05$, H_0 is accepted), partially the effect of Desire is not significant on YouTube Adoption.

- Needs significance value is 0.228 ($0.228 > 0.05$, H_0 is accepted), partially the influence of Needs is not significant on YouTube Adoption.
- The significance value of motive is 0.673 ($0.673 > 0.05$, H_0 is accepted), partially the influence of motive is not significant on YouTube adoption.
- Satisfaction has a significance value of 0.002 ($0.002 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected), partially the effect of satisfaction is significant on YouTube adoption.

Based on table 4.7 above, the regression equation model between TV user satisfaction and adoption of YouTube media can be obtained: $Y = 58.844 - 0.8571 - 0,546 X_2 + 0,224 X_3 + 2,014 X_4$.

Interpretation:

- 1) The desire coefficient is -0.875, meaning that if the desire value increases by 1, the YouTube adoption value will decrease by 0.875.
- 2) The need coefficient is -0.546, meaning that if the need value increases by 1, the YouTube adoption value will decrease by 0.546.
- 3) The Motive coefficient is 0.224, meaning that if the Motive value increases by 1, the YouTube adoption value will increase by 0.224.
- 4) The satisfaction coefficient is 2.014, meaning that if the satisfaction value increases by 1, the YouTube adoption value will increase by 2.014

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The results of this analysis show that, satisfaction users TV has a significant influence on YouTube adoption among members of the Kabar Cipanas Facebook group (H_a rejected). This means that TV users feel that their satisfaction in seeking information and entertainment on television is not fulfilled. So, users look for other media to fulfill their satisfaction. Until, in the end, they adopted YouTube media to fulfill the information and entertainment satisfaction they needed. This becomes warning for television, which is a conventional information and entertainment medium, to increase user satisfaction so that they remain loyal to using television.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of The Influence of Television User Satisfaction on Youtube Media Adoption in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

REFERENCES

- Apriyono, A., & Taman, A. (2013). Journal Noun / Volume Ii Number Ii / Year 2013 76 Analysis of Overreaction in Manufacturing Company Shares on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) Period. II(2), 19.
- Badrudin, S. (2017). An-Nur Community Television Da'wah Communication Strategy, Palembang Grand Mosque. Journal of Islamic Communication and Public Relations, 1(2), 2.
- Denziana, A., Indrayenti, & Fatah, F. (2014). Corporate Financial Performance effect of Marco Economic Factors Against Stock Return. Journal of Accounting & Finance, IN(2), 23.
- Fitria, S. E., & Ariva, V. F. (2018). Factor Analysis of Economic Conditions, Level of Education and Entrepreneurial Ability on Business Performance for Pindang Entrepreneurs in Cukanggenteng Village. Indonesian Management Journal, XVIII(3), 200. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jmi.v18i3.1732>
- Imran, H. A. (2017). The Role of Sampling and Data Distribution in Communication Research Quantitative Approach). Journal of Communication and Media Studies, XXI(1), 114.
- Karman. (2013). Research on Media Uses and Its Development - Researches on Media Uses and Its Development. Journal of Communication and Media Studies, XVII(1), 93-94.
- Latifah, E. (2020). The Effectiveness of Tabayyun in Online Media for the Millennial Generation. Journal of Islamic Communication and Broadcasting, IV(1), 19. <http://ejournal.iai-tabah.ac.id/index.php/alamtaraok/article/view/498>
- Rahmawati, Y., Maduwinarti, A., & Norhabiba, F. (2020). The Effect of Exposure to the Head & Shoulders Shampoo Advertisement "Joe Taslim's Version of the Move On Bro Slogan" on the Perceptions of Untag Surabaya Communication Science Students. Communication Studies, 45, 3. <http://repository.untag-sby.ac.id/5867/62/JURNAL.pdf>
- Ratu, R., Koleangan, R. A. M., & Kojo, C. (2020). The Influence of Work Experience and Human Resource Competency on Employee Performance at the Dabu-Dabu Lemong Restaurant in Manado. EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research, VII(1), 454. <https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.v8i1.27782>
- Riyanto. (2017). Effectiveness of Internet Media on Media Audience Satisfaction. InterCommunication, II(1), 64. <https://doi.org/10.33376/ik.v2i1.16>
- Sabrudin, D., & Suhendra, E. S. (2019). The Impact of Accountability, Transparency and Pedagogical Professionalism on Teacher Performance at SMKN 21 Jakarta. Nusantara Journal Business Management Applications, IV(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.29407/nusamba.v4i1.12848>
- Sari, M., & Asmendri. (2020). Library Research (Library Research) in Science Education Research. Library Research (Library Research) in Science Education Research, WE(1), 15. <https://journal.uinib.ac.id/journal/i>

- index.php/naturalscience/article/view/1555/1159Stellarosa, Y., Firyal, S. J., & Ikhsano,
- A. (2018). Utilization of YouTube as a Means of Transforming Highend Magazines.LUGAS Communication Journal, II(2), 59-68. <https://doi.org/10.31334/ljk.v2i2.263>
- Supriyadi, E., Mariani, S., & Sugiman. (2017). Comparison of Partial Least Square (Pls) and Principal Component Regression (Pcr) Methods to Overcome Multicollinearity in Multiple Linear Regression Models.Unnes Journal of Mathematics, WE(2), 122.<https://doi.org/10.15294/ujm.v6i2.11819>
- Yasya, W., Muljono, P., & Seminar, K. B. (2019). Influence Use of Facebook Social Media and Online Social Support on Breastfeeding Behavior Effects of Facebook Social Media Use and Online Social Support. XXIII, 72.
- Zahra, R. R., & Rina, N. (2018). The Influence of Celebrity Endorser Hamidah Rachmayanti on Decisions to Purchase Mayoutfit Online Shop Products in Bandung City.Lontar Journal of Communication Sciences, WE(9), 50.
- Zulfah, S. (2018). The Influence of Environmental Information Technology Development (Case Study of Siti Rejo I Village, Medan).Primary Journal of Engineering, XIII(2), 2. <https://jurnal.uisu.ac.id/index.php/but/article/view/284>
- Courbuzier, D. (2018).Youtuber For Dummies. Jakarta: Bhuana Popular Science.
- Yusuf, M. A. (2014). Quantitative, Qualitative and Combined Research Methods. Jakarta: Kencana Prenadamedia Group.
- Bungin, M. B. (2017).Quantitative Research Methods.Jakarta: Kencana Prenadamedia Group.
- Nasrullah, R. (2019).Media Audience Theory and Research.Jakarta: Kencana Prenadamedia Group.
- Good luck. (2015).Introduction to Anthropology.Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.
- Mustafa, P. S., Gusdiyanto, H., & Victoria, A. (2020). Quantitative, Qualitative Research and Classroom Action Research Methodologies in Sports Education.Malang: State University of Malang.
- Romli, K. (2016).Mass communication.Jakarta: PT Garsindo.
- Panji, M. R. (2017).Household Preparedness in Facing Landslide Disasters in Cipanas District, Cianjur Regency.Bandung: Indonesian Education University.